

Building Competitive Advantage: Lesson Learned from “PT Nestlé Indonesia”

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Abstract

Competitive advantage or competitive advantage is the ability of a company to achieve economic profits above the profits achieved by competitors in the market in the same industry. Companies that have a competitive advantage always have the ability to understand changes in market structure and are able to choose effective marketing strategies. Furthermore, it is explained that competitive advantage develops from the value that a company is able to create for customers or buyers. The purpose of this business strategy analysis is to understand the business environment within PT Nestlé internally and externally. The business environment is very influential in strategic planning as an opportunity to neutralize threats and long-term development of a company. PT Nestlé's requirement in planning its competitive needs in the market is to look at the business environment to provide an idea of what strategy it will take. However, PT Nestlé's business strategy has not been optimally used by the company to develop globally. Strategy formulation is crucial in facing complex business challenges. Nestlé must formulate a strategy that not only includes financial aspects, but also considers the social and environmental impacts of its business decisions. This strategy needs to be able to overcome market dynamics, maintain competitive advantage, and be in line with the company's sustainability mission. Environmental analysis provides invaluable insight into identifying opportunities and threats. Effective control is necessary to ensure sustainability and positive development. Efficient operational aspects support the achievement of company goals. Proactive and responsive management is the key to success in facing ever-changing challenges in the global market. Overall, Nestlé as a leading company must continue to carry out a thorough evaluation of its strategy and operations, focus on sustainability, and maintain a balance between economic growth, social responsibility and environmental sustainability.

Keywords: Strategy, Competitive Advantage, PT Nestlé Indonesia

Introduction

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2012), competitive advantage is an advantage over competitors that is obtained by offering lower value or by providing greater benefits because the price is higher. Using this theory, you must be able to consider what aspects will be offered

at a low value but with greater benefits. For example, offering a cheap registration fee but the program being implemented is still good, maybe even the same as a program that is expensive¹. The role of competitive advantage is very important in company performance. Competitive advantage comes from the company's many activities in designing, producing, marketing, delivering and supporting the products or services produced. Competitive advantage or competitive advantage is the ability of a company to achieve economic profits above the profits achieved by competitors in the market in the same industry. Companies that have a competitive advantage always have the ability to understand changes in market structure and are able to choose effective marketing strategies. Furthermore, it is explained that competitive advantage develops from the value that a company is able to create for customers or buyers (Porter, 2008).

Strategic management is a comprehensive process of systematic activities from a continuous process that is being used in the implementation and monitoring of strategy creation. The strategic management function in the company is very helpful for the continuity of the company's life. Not only as a static plan to realize the company's vision and mission, strategy is a management function that must be implemented in an organization. The basic functions that must be implemented are marketing, operational and financial functions. Strategic management can be defined as the art and science of formulating, implementing and evaluating cross-functional decisions that enable an organization to achieve its goals.² Strategic management focuses on integrating management, marketing, finance and accounting, production and operations, research and development , as well as information systems to achieve organizational success. The term strategic management is used synonymously with the term strategic planning. The latter term is more often used in the business world, while the former is often used in the academic world (Warlizasusi, 2018,).

The term strategic management is used with reference to the formulation, implementation, and evaluation of strategies, while strategic planning refers only to strategy formulation. The goal of strategic management is to find and create new and different opportunities for tomorrow, long-range planning, on the other hand, tries to optimize tomorrow's trends based on today's trends. Nestlé was chosen as the research object because it is one of the global companies that has succeeded in building competitive advantages and is committed to sustainability principles. With its diverse products and worldwide presence, Nestlé offers a rich case study for understanding how strategy and strategic management can support sustainability and competitive advantage in the food and beverage industry. Even though Nestlé has achieved success, this company also faces a number of problems, especially in the context of increasingly fierce competition. With competition in the global market continuing to grow, Nestlé is faced with pressure to continue to improve its competitiveness. This company needs to develop a new strategy to overcome these problems and ensure its survival amidst rapidly changing market dynamics.

The purpose of this business strategy analysis is to understand the business environment within PT Nestlé internally and externally. The business environment is very influential in strategic planning as an opportunity to neutralize threats and long-term development of a company.³ PT Nestlé's requirement in planning its competitive needs in the market is to look at the business environment to provide an idea of what strategy it will take. However, PT Nestle's business strategy has not been optimally used by the company to develop globally. Through this

background discussion, we will understand the context of the importance of competitive advantage, sustainability and strategy in the Nestlé context and identify the challenges the company faces in building and maintaining its competitiveness. This article discusses Nestlé's Strategy in Building Competitive Advantage, Corporate Social Responsibility, and Responsible Environmental Management to Increase Sustainability 1. To understand Nestlé's Vision, Mission, Goals and Strategy? 2. To analyze Nestlé's External and Internal Environment? 3. To find out Strategy Implementation in the Management aspect and other aspects that stand out from Nestlé? 4. To find out about Nestlé's Evaluation and Control? 5. To analyze the Social Responsibility carried out by Nestlé? 6. To analyze strategies to achieve long-term survival (sustainability) for Nestlé?

Literature Review

Understanding Strategic Management

Strategic management is a planned and organized approach to managing an organization's resources and activities to achieve its long-term goals (Kotler, 2005). Meanwhile, David (2017) states that strategic management is a process that can help organizations identify opportunities and challenges in the environment, as well as formulate goals and strategies to take advantage of opportunities and overcome challenges. This concept includes planning, implementing and monitoring strategies designed to optimize organizational performance and competitiveness. In the context of Nestlé, this company applies strategic management as a basis for high-level decision making to achieve its long-term goals.

Vision and Mission

Vision, according to Edison et al (2018), is a statement or goal that the organization wants to achieve in the future and is more concentrated on long-term programs. Missions are statements that state the main function. Which is the basis of the existence of the organization. Vision, according to Edison et al (2018), is a statement or goal that an organization/organization wants to achieve in the future and is more concentrated on long-term programs. According to Peter Drucker (2000:87) as quoted in Nawawi (2017:14), basically mission is "the fundamental reason for the existence of an organization". Meanwhile, according to Edison et al (2018:26), the mission is "a statement that states the main function, which is the reason for the existence of the organization". The strategic management process begins with identifying the company's vision and mission, which provides long-term direction and goals. After that, the company carries out an analysis of the internal and external environment to understand internal strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that might affect operations. Nestlé carefully measures these aspects, ensuring that the strategies it adopts match market dynamics and the company's internal strengths.

The Importance of Internal and External Environmental Analysis

According to Wispandono, (2010), the organizational environment within a company is known as the internal environment. The purpose of this research is to identify the organization's relative strengths and weaknesses when compared to its competitors. This leads us to the conclusion that

a company's internal environment is the setting in which it operates, where its constituent parts either directly or indirectly support the organization. Kotler and Keller (2016) state that the external environment consists of uncontrollable macroeconomic forces that influence organizations and industries. While Hoskisson et al., (2016) underlined that the external environment includes factors such as opportunities and threats, as well as economic, social, cultural, demographic, political, legal, technological and ecological elements. The external environment is everything that exists outside the walls of an organization and has the potential to have an impact on it. Therefore, to function and compete in an environment, managers must understand it fully and appropriately. To identify the possibilities and risks faced by the company, it is necessary to assess the external environment, namely the environment around the organization. It can be concluded that the external environment can be defined as the environment outside the corporation that has the potential to directly or indirectly influence how the company operates and present possibilities or dangers to the organization.

Strategy Implementation in Management Aspects and Operational Issues

Operations Strategy The vision of the operations function, or operations strategy, sets the general direction or motivation for decision making. An organization's business strategy, price reduction, and price matching are all supported by its operational strategy, which consists of a set of objectives, strategies, and procedures. Strong indications can serve as a foundation for business expansion and success (Purwidiyanti et al., 2015).

Research and Development (R&D) Aspects

R&D managers need to adapt complex technologies or develop new technologies to successfully implement strategies. Research and development staff have a crucial role in strategy implementation, as they can create innovative products and improve existing products, which in turn increases the effectiveness of strategy implementation. Success in developing new product strategies and market penetration can be achieved through three main approaches to research and development. First, become a pioneer in marketing new technology-based products. Second, adopt the approach of being an innovative copycat of a successful product to reduce risks and initial costs. Third, become a low-cost producer with similar products that are mass-produced, but at a more affordable price compared to products newly introduced by other companies.

Evaluation

Evaluation according to Suryana, (2014), explains the level of change brought about in business by implementing new concepts. Evaluation and organizational performance are correlated; the more company evaluations, the more successful the company as a whole. Evaluation is the result of analyzing the market environment to help businesses understand what customers want while generating new ideas to improve services and drive business success. Strategic evaluation helps an organization in shaping its future direction, enabling optimal utilization of internal strengths and external opportunities, as well as protecting itself from threats and minimizing internal weaknesses. One of the crucial strategic evaluation activities is assessing organizational performance. Performance evaluation is an assessment carried out by a company or individual

to evaluate the work results of employees and the organization as a whole. Company management should conduct a performance assessment to identify weaknesses, strengths, errors and other factors that may affect the company's performance in the future. Performance evaluation is not only useful for identifying problems, but can also be used to correct policies and work patterns that are not in accordance with work conditions or company conditions. Job evaluation results can be divided into two, namely positive and negative. Positive results will be improved to achieve better performance in the future, while negative results will be improved or eliminated. Therefore, performance evaluation is an important action for companies to achieve success and sustainable growth. Apart from carrying out evaluations, companies also need to carry out controls to ensure that all business activities run in accordance with the stated objectives.

DISCUSSION: PT Nestle profile

PT Nestlé Indonesia is a company that produces the largest food in the world and focuses on nutrition and health for quality consumer needs (Purwidiyanti et al., 2015). Nestlé is a multinational company operating in the food and beverage sector. Nestlé is the world's largest company in terms of revenue from sales of food and beverage products. Nestlé operates in more than 180 countries and has more than 280,000 employees. Nestlé was founded in 1866 by Henri Nestlé, a Swiss pharmacist. Nestlé initially produced baby porridge to help children who were unable to breastfeed. The company then expanded to produce a variety of food and beverage products, including milk, coffee, tea, candy and snacks. Nestlé owns a variety of world-famous brands, including Nescafé, Nespresso, KitKat, Maggi and Gerber. The company also invests in research and development to continuously innovate and improve its products.

Nestle's Vision and Mission

The following is Nestlé's Vision and Mission:

Nestlé Vision: To be the world's leading food and beverage company with a commitment to improving the quality of life and contributing to a healthier future.

Nestlé's mission: To provide high-quality food and beverages that are safe, nutritious and affordable to people around the world.

Strategic Management and Competitive Advantage

The relationship between strategic management and competitive advantage is the key to Nestlé's success in global market dynamics. Strategic management is the foundation that supports and enables companies to build and maintain their competitive advantage. In the context of Nestlé, strategic decisions, especially those related to product innovation and marketing strategy, play a central role in shaping and enhancing the company's competitive advantage.

1. Strategic Decisions in Product Innovation:

Nestlé consistently demonstrates its commitment to product innovation. The strategic decision to continuously develop and launch new products allows Nestlé to maintain consumer interest, meet market trends, and even create new demand. Thus, strategic management here becomes

the main bearer of competitive advantage, because innovative products provide advantages over competitors and strengthen Nestlé's brand image.

2. Defensible Marketing Strategy:

Nestlé's strategic management is related to a well-planned marketing strategy. Decisions in designing marketing campaigns, pricing, and product distribution support a company's efforts to differentiate itself from competitors. Sustaining an effective marketing strategy helps build brand awareness, increases consumer loyalty, and provides a strong foundation for competitive advantage.

3. Emphasis on Quality and Added Value:

Nestlé's competitive advantage is also reflected in its emphasis on the quality and added value of its products. Wise strategic management directs companies to focus on providing products that not only meet basic needs but also provide added value to consumers. This creates additional differentiation and attractiveness, supporting Nestlé's competitive advantage in a crowded market.

4. Compliance with Changing Business Environment:

The relationship between strategic management and competitive advantage also includes the company's adaptation to changes in the business environment. Nestlé understands that changes in markets, technology and consumer preferences can impact competitiveness. Therefore, quick and appropriate strategic decisions are taken to adapt and stay relevant in the ever-changing market.

By explaining the close relationship between strategic management and competitive advantage, this chapter will provide insight into how Nestlé designs and implements strategies holistically to strengthen its position in the global food and beverage market. This company's success in utilizing strategic management to support its competitive advantage is the core of the in-depth discussion in this chapter.

The Importance of Internal and External Environmental Analysis at Nestlé

Analysis of the internal and external environment is an important step in formulating corporate strategy. For Nestlé, a deep understanding of internal and external factors through SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) analysis and PESTLE (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, Environmental) analysis is a critical basis for designing effective strategic plans. According to Wispandono, (2010), the organizational environment within a company is known as the internal environment. The purpose of this research is to identify the organization's relative strengths and weaknesses when compared to its competitors. This leads us to the conclusion that a company's internal environment is the setting in which it operates, where its constituent parts either directly or indirectly support the organization.

According to Saputra (2015), the external environment is everything that exists outside the walls of the organization and has the potential to have an impact on it. Therefore, to function and compete in an environment, managers must understand it fully and appropriately. To identify the possibilities and risks faced by the company, it is necessary to assess the external environment, namely the environment around the organization. It can be concluded that the external environment can be defined as the environment outside the corporation that has the

potential to directly or indirectly influence how the company operates and present possibilities or dangers to the organization.

Internal Analysis

Internal environmental analysis at PT Nestlé Indonesia is a factor that occurs or arises from the company itself. These factors are as follows:

1. Sales

Sales of Nestlé products throughout the world are quite good, for example sales of Nestlé products in China. Nestlé's sales in China increased 12%-13% compared to 2008. Last year, Nestlé China achieved record sales of up to 2.23 billion Swiss francs or 2.1 billion US dollars. This amount represents 2% of Nestlé's global sales in 2008. This is internally related to the Chinese government's policy of providing several subsidies to boost domestic consumption, encouraging Nestlé S.A. sales. lifted (Nuramdhani, 2019). Nestlé can take advantage of the popular policies of the Chinese government. Currently Nestlé China has 21 factories and sells various kinds of food and drinks. Coffee, broth, milk and ice cream are the most widely sold foods in the country of one billion people. That's why Nestlé didn't hesitate to build one of the largest broth factories in the world. The factory, which invested 320 million yuan, can produce 100,000 tons of stock per year. The establishment of a chalk factory is Nestlé's way of increasing its production capacity for key products. This policy also emphasizes that acquiring food businesses is not a priority (Nuramdhani, 2019). Based on global sales results of the product portfolio produced by the Nestle company, less than 30% of sales products do not meet health standards. It is the strict externals that dominate indulgent products, such as ice cream, chocolate, etc. (Nestlé, 2021).

2. Marketing

In marketing, PT Nestlé has built its own distribution channel which provides various products that can be purchased anywhere, anytime by consumers. These sales are subject to available inventory. Based on market research, PT Nestlé has shown that there have been more than 60 purchases, which means that Nestle has spread its products to all existing outlets through seller and retailer channels. Nestlé also has a good marketing mix strategy so that when carrying out marketing in the field there are no big difficulties. The growth of the Nestlé brand through advertising plays an important role in increasing the branding of Nestlé products. So Nestlé itself spreads advertisements for their products throughout the world to increase sales. Nestlé has a database that contains codes to be able to buy their products in one country by buying the same product in another country. Nestlé will also know how many purchases made by consumers can be accessed by a single account. Therefore, purchases between countries can be easier to carry out and coordinate, because Nestlé implements a centralized negotiation process that provides a larger volume than one-by-one purchases. In this way, Nestlé can carry out marketing more efficiently.

3. Financial Resources

Regulations regarding Financial Resources at the PT Nestlé company have been regulated by a clear information system, with a system that has been developed by Nestle, therefore data from Nestlé's financial resources in various branches spread throughout the world can be managed

well by the head office. The financial reports of each branch at PT Nestlé are reported once a week. By implementing this, the central Nestlé will control its finances well so that it can avoid a span of control in its finances.

4. Human Resources

Of course, Nestlé needs resources in the form of human resources, infrastructure and knowledge. Nestlé formed its own logistics team to provide sufficient support for implementation at Nestlé. Nestlé management will be responsible for providing these human resources. Basically, this logistics team is led by top management who will take full responsibility as a mediator between top management and other teams. Top management is usually people who are experienced and understand the ins and outs of the business they run, understand what to do and what not to do, and can handle dissatisfaction from customers and employees. Apart from that, PT Nestlé usually always carries out open recruitment which is different in each location and the company always prioritizes people who live in that country to recruit employees according to the company culture in that country. However, the Nestlé company always brings its experts from their country of origin, because the human resources of each country are different.

5. Research and Development

Before introducing a product, PT Nestlé certainly carries out surveys and research on the target market for the product that will be released in order to find out the strengths and weaknesses of the product, so that later the product released will be satisfied when received by consumers. Nestlé also conducts market tests for its products before the product is actually marketed widely.

External Analysis

The purpose of external environmental analysis is to identify potential threats and opportunities for the company. Threats refer to general conditions in the environment that can hinder a company's ability to compete strategically, while opportunities refer to conditions in the general environment that can help a company achieve strategic advantage. To carry out continuous analysis of the external environment, several processes can be carried out such as scanning, monitoring, forecasting and assessing.

1. Macro Environment

In the context of the macro environment, Nestlé takes technological, government, economic, cultural and demographic factors as marketing strategies in each country.

a. Technology

In environmental analysis, one important aspect is the technological trends developing in the market or industry and their impact on business strategy. The progress of innovation, especially in the field of information wise can influence business associations. For example, business association activities compare creation steps with the use of innovative and complex machines reducing human error and lowering manufacturing costs (Singh et al., 2021). Nestlé pays attention to this and strives to create new technologies that create a positive environmental impact. Nestlé recognizes that technological change can be an opportunity or a threat, so employees are provided with training to cope with the transition to new technology.

Nestlé uses information technology systems as a competitive advantage by utilizing a corporate intranet called Nestlé Intranet Kit Assistant (NIKITA). More than 80,000 employees throughout the Nestlé company use NIKITA for business activities such as purchasing, marketing, business intelligence, technology and human resource management. Nestlé introduces technological

changes in a gradual and controlled manner to achieve better results, so that it does not directly impact all products.

b. Government

The government has a significant role in Nestlé's activities. As a supervisor, the government is responsible for enforcing applicable regulations. Policies issued by the government can affect PT Nestlé's operations. In this function, the government will publish laws and regulations that can have an impact on PT Nestlé through BUMN. PT Nestlé Indonesia, as a company operating in Indonesia, will be affected by the policies announced by the government. Some of these policies include:

1. Tax policy: Nestlé Indonesia must comply with the tax regulations applicable in Indonesia and pay taxes in accordance with the provisions set by the government.
2. International trade policy: International trade policy can affect the availability of raw materials and the prices that Nestlé Indonesia must pay to produce its products.
3. Environmental policy: The Indonesian government has strict regulations regarding waste management and environmental protection. Nestlé Indonesia must comply with these regulations to maintain the company's credibility and legality..
4. Employment policy: Nestlé Indonesia must comply with applicable employment regulations in Indonesia, including following minimum wage standards and providing employee rights.
5. Investment policy: Nestlé Indonesia must comply with government regulations regarding investment and licensing to carry out its operations in Indonesia.

Therefore, Nestlé managers must understand the government's decision-making process. Although the government is expected to act fairly, decisions taken may be influenced by conflicting interests, so Nestlé managers must be prepared to take appropriate anticipatory action.

c. Economy

To evaluate a strategy, it is necessary to consider economic aspects such as inflation, unemployment rates, and a country's economic growth. Companies must also consider both material and non-material aspects, including that the company they run must receive aspirations from the community, and if the business is unable to meet community needs, it will not strive for profitability (Singh et al., 2021). As a company in the food and beverage sector, Nestlé must pay attention to national economic conditions which can affect the performance of PT Nestlé Indonesia. When the economy is growing, people's purchasing power increases and consumption of Nestlé products tends to increase as well. However, if economic conditions decline, people's purchasing power will also decrease, so demand for Nestlé products may decrease. This is what makes economic factors a factor that greatly influences the sustainability of a company. Financial constraints are an important way to evaluate the effectiveness of the Nestle company, because their target market is the upper class and middle class who have enough money to consume their products. In fact, income level is a major factor in determining the price of a commodity, which will play a role in determining income, profits and product competitiveness. Price fluctuations and economic conditions such as inflation also have a major impact on a company's profitability. Apart from that, recognizing and taking into account the large scale of production when organizing and managing it is also a factor that cannot be

ignored. Through concentrated operations throughout the world, Nestle has managed to counteract the effects of volatility in foreign investment markets on export trade markets.

d. Social and Cultural

Social culture is a combination of various values, ideologies, beliefs, behavior patterns, ideas and attitudes that are found collectively. In a corporate context, cultural change can bring both risks and opportunities, depending on the fit with the company itself. If Nestlé wants to open a branch factory in a country, it needs to consider the corporate culture that applies in that country. Apart from that, Nestlé must always pay attention to the cultural developments of the people in that country so that it can adapt its products and pricing strategies to suit the market needs in that country. For example, Indonesian business patterns and consumer habits can influence PT Nestlé Indonesia's business, such as Indonesian people's habits in consuming food and drinks, such as taste and nutritional content, must be taken into account when developing new products. Another example of the culture of Indonesian society, which predominantly adheres to Islam, is that there must be a HALAL label issued by the MUI (Indonesian Ulema Council) as well as a BPOM label issued by the Food and Drug Monitoring Agency on the packaging of products circulating in Indonesia. All R&D companies operating in Indonesia must comply with this regulation in order to enter the market in Indonesia.

e. Demographics

Market success can be influenced by significant demographic trends. Demographic variables such as age, income, education and geographic location can be important factors in expanding the market for Nestlé products. Nestlé also conducts surveys and research in certain countries by taking into account factors such as population, per capita income, age, gender, and others to determine the right product price. Initially, Nestlé only targeted children and parents as the target market for their product, namely Milo, but now almost all Nestlé products cover all age groups. Nestlé's market area is segmented for its main products by generation. For example, for Cerelac, Lactogen, Koko Krunch, Nido, Nestlé products divide the market segments into newborns and children of various ages (Hossain Reza, 2020).

2. Micro Environment

In the context of the micro environment, Nestlé takes the factors of competition between industries, consumer and purchasing behavior, and new entrants as marketing strategies in each country.

a. Inter-Industry Competition

Nestlé has aggressively developed and expanded its product range, launching dozens of products with hundreds of varieties. Thanks to strong distribution and the right marketing concept, almost all Nestlé products are successful in the market. As a leader in the food and beverage industry, Nestlé really understands consumer desires and its strategy of extracting products based on flavors from various countries has proven successful. In Indonesia itself, PT Nestlé Indonesia has big competitors in the same industry such as PT Indofood Tbk and Unilever. This kind of competition can affect the prices of products and services, as well as company profits.

b. Consumers and Behavior

Nestlé purchases as a multinational company, has a large market share because it has various types of different products, such as coffee, chocolate, cereal, milk, and so on. Because each Nestlé product is aimed at a different target market, this has an impact on the number of Nestlé consumers continuing to increase.

Consumers are a key factor in the food and beverage industry, and PT Nestlé Indonesia must understand their needs and preferences well. Additionally, changes in consumer purchasing behavior, such as increased health awareness and environmental concern, can influence demand for products and services. Nestlé is always successful in every country because it always pays attention to the taste preferences of local consumers. Each country has different tastes in terms of taste and price, therefore Nestlé is committed to adapting its products so that they can be accepted and enjoyed by consumers in each different country, thereby creating consumer satisfaction.

c. New entrants

Even though Nestlé is a company that controls almost half of the F&B market, it still does not rule out the possibility of the emergence of new entrants who could shift Nestlé's position in the market. New entrants can affect Nestlé in several ways, namely if new competitors introduce new products that are more innovative, attractive and relevant to consumers, offer lower costs or more attractive sales promotions then this can threaten Nestlé's market share. An increase in new competitors may also reduce demand for Nestlé products already established in the market. However, PT Nestlé Indonesia has advantages in terms of brand, reputation, established distribution network, and ability to carry out continuous product innovation. Additionally, they can also offer better services to their customers. This can be an advantage that can make consumers remain loyal and choose Nestlé products over new competitors' products.

SWOT Analysis

To be able to compete in the global market, multinational companies like Nestlé must analyze their own products through detailed research and analysis that includes SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats)

1. Strengths:

Judging from the marketing goals of each company, business collaboration capabilities are very important. Using a simple SWOT analysis will improve any business and manager it chooses to lead. A company's ability to position its products depends on the ability and satisfaction of consumers with their needs. This is the value achieved in marketing, including revenue and market share, competitive analysis, sales, future profits, and analysis of changes in consumer behavior (Nuramdhani, 2019).

a. Nestlé has a broad and diverse product portfolio in various market segments.

b. Strong brand image and consumer trust in product quality.

2. Weaknesses:

There are rarely shortages of Nestlé products because we continuously monitor changes in market demand and consumer tastes. Meeting consumer needs is critical to business success. However, on closer inspection, sales declined in 1999 due to weak Nestlé sales. We know from the trade press that young people don't like Nestlé and prefer other brands. It is known that

young people of that time did not like Nestlé and they preferred other signs which they thought made more sense to their souls. To overcome this problem, Nestlé introduced modern products that are more suitable for young people.

- a. Depends on a few superior products, making it vulnerable to market fluctuations.
- b. Depends on some specific regional markets.

3. Opportunities:

Nestlé benefits from its reputation as a leading dairy company and is the largest company in the world. Open belief in the universality or quality of its products must be maintained so that public interest in Nestlé products becomes "the second best breast milk absorbent for babies (leading)". Nestlé has the opportunity to be known throughout the world for its health-based products, including in the United States. Buyers are increasingly health conscious and understand that life expectancy is unfair due to luck and heredity.

- a. Growth of the healthy and functional food and beverage market.
- b. Potential for expansion into growing global markets.

4. Threats:

Nestlé believes Danone will partner with this brand under the name Kit Kat. This will result in negligence and damage Nestlé's reputation. This condition is clearly concerning, because the first brand to use it was Nestlé. These challenges are so extreme that complaints have been filed with the Directorate General of Intellectual Property Rights, specifically the Department of Trademarks. The price of cleaning products is also usually more expensive than products from other comparable brands, so they do not reach all groups. Customers find Nestlé products expensive and therefore switch to other products.

- a. Tight competition in the food and beverage industry.
- b. Fluctuations in raw material prices and global economic factors.

SWOT analysis helps Nestlé to understand its relative position in the market, identify competitive advantages, and address weaknesses that could affect its long-term strategy.

PESTLE analysis

PESTLE analysis helps Nestlé understand and respond to the dynamics of the external environment, including political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental changes. It provides insight into opportunities and threats that can impact a company's strategy and operations.

1. Political:

International trade policies and food regulations in each country where Nestlé operates.

2. Economy:

The effect of changes in currency exchange rates on production costs and profit margins.

Changing consumer trends regarding health and eating patterns.

3. Technological:

Technological advances in production and distribution that can increase operational efficiency.

4. Legal

Food regulations and food safety that apply in each market.

5. Environmental

Pressure to reduce environmental impact through sustainable production practices.

By conducting internal and external environmental analysis, Nestlé can identify relevant factors for strategic decision making, design strategies that are responsive to market changes, and ensure long-term sustainability and growth.

Strategy Implementation in Management Aspects and Operational Issues

In this part the focus will be placed on how Nestlé manages strategy implementation through various aspects of company management and operations.

1. Strategic Management:

Top Management Role: Nestlé's leaders and high-level executives play a central role in communicating and ensuring a consistent understanding of the company's strategy. They are responsible for designing and directing the overall implementation of the strategy.

2. Strategy Integration in Organizational Structure:

Nestlé ensures that strategy is effectively integrated into the organizational structure. This includes defining responsibilities, team structure, and relationships between business units to ensure efficient collaboration.

3. Operational Aspects:

Product Development and Innovation: Strategy implementation in the operational sector includes product development and innovation efforts. Nestlé focuses on managing its supply chain, production processes and operational improvements to support new product launches and ensure their quality.

4. Marketing and Branding:

Marketing strategies are implemented by creating creative and effective campaigns. Nestlé strives to build and maintain its brand image through marketing that is closely linked to the company's values.

5. Human Resources (HR):

Employee training and competency development programs are an integral part of HR strategy implementation. Nestlé manages employee aspects by ensuring the availability of appropriate skills and strong engagement.

6. Special Initiatives:

Sustainability Programs: Nestlé may have prominent sustainability initiatives, such as reducing its carbon footprint, managing plastic waste, or engaging in social initiatives. Such initiatives reflect the company's commitment to social and environmental responsibility.

7. Specific Marketing Campaigns:

If there are any prominent marketing campaigns, such as a recent product launch or charity campaign, these can be discussed to provide concrete examples of marketing strategy implementation.

Evaluation of Company Success (Management and R&D Aspects)

Management Aspects

This part will discuss how Nestlé evaluates the success of its strategy through specific performance parameters.

1. Sales Growth:

Nestlé will evaluate sales growth as an indicator of the success of marketing strategies and new products. Increased sales can show the effectiveness of the strategy in attracting consumers.

2. Market Share:

Market share is an important benchmark, showing the extent to which Nestlé can maintain or improve its position in the market against competitors.

3. Profitability:

Profitability evaluation involves analyzing net income, profit margins, and rate of return on investment. This provides an overview of operational efficiency and strategic success in generating profits.

1. Product Innovation and Response to Trends:

Success in launching innovative products and response to market trends can be measured to assess the extent to which Nestlé can anticipate and meet consumer needs.

5. Environmental and Social Performance:

If Nestlé is committed to sustainability and social responsibility, the company's performance evaluation will include positive impacts on the environment and contributions to society.

R&D aspect

The Research and Development (R&D) aspect at PT Nestle involves a series of activities aimed at creating innovation, improving product quality, and ensuring the company's sustainable growth. The following are several aspects of R&D related to PT Nestle:

1. Product Innovation:

PT Nestle continues to conduct research to develop new products that meet customer needs and the latest market trends. This includes the discovery of new raw materials, innovative product formulations, and the development of product variants.

2. Quality Improvement:

Focus on R&D also includes efforts to continuously improve the quality of existing products. PT Nestle is committed to providing high quality and safe products for consumers, as well as ensuring compliance with food safety standards.

3. Collaboration with External Parties:

PT Nestle can establish partnerships and collaborations with research institutions, universities and other industrial partners to expand the network of knowledge and resources that support innovation.

4. Latest Production Technology:

The company invests resources in research into the latest production technologies to improve operational efficiency and ensure that products are manufactured using the most advanced methods.

5. Sustainability:

PT Nestle can also place emphasis on research to develop more environmentally friendly production methods and reduce the environmental impact of the company's activities.

6. Adaptation to Market Trends:

R&D can focus on understanding and adapting to market trends, such as consumer demand for organic, functional, or sustainable products.

7. Compliance with Regulatory Standards:

PT Nestle conducts research to ensure that all products and production processes comply with applicable regulatory standards and legal requirements.

8. Development of Efficient Production Processes:

Innovation can also include developing more efficient production processes to reduce production costs and increase competitiveness.

9. Market Research:

R&D may engage in market research to understand consumer preferences, market trends, and needs that may arise in the future.

By combining these aspects, PT Nestle can ensure that its R&D division plays an important role in driving company growth, maintaining product competitiveness, and meeting consumer expectations. Then discussing strategy implementation on various operational aspects and performance evaluation criteria, this chapter provides a comprehensive overview of how Nestlé not only plans and formulates strategies, but also measures and evaluates its success in the global food and beverage market.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Analysis

Nestlé is committed to improving the quality of life and contributing to a healthier future. The company believes that food and drink play an important role in people's health and well-being. Nestlé works to ensure that its products are safe, nutritious and affordable for people around the world. Nestlé is also committed to sustainability. The company believes that businesses must be sustainable to survive and thrive in the long term. Nestlé works to reduce the environmental impact of its business and to improve the well-being of society.

Nestlé, as a leading company in the global food and beverage industry, carries out careful internal and external environmental analysis. A deep understanding of a company's internal strengths and weaknesses is a focus, along with responding to changes in the external environment such as market trends, regulations and consumer behavior. And Nestlé is engaged in a restructuring process to adapt to market changes and improve operational efficiency. Restructuring efforts involve reviewing the business model and necessary organizational changes.

Nestlé continuously evaluates and controls to ensure business continuity. This process involves a thorough analysis of the company's performance and the implementation of necessary corrective actions, as discussed in the previous week's evaluation. Nestlé is also active in corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities with a focus on making positive contributions to society and the environment. Companies realize the important role of CSR in providing a positive impact, not only related to business sustainability, but also moral and ethical responsibilities towards global society. In facing future challenges, Nestlé has a clear strategy to achieve long-term sustainability. This includes developing strategies for sustainability with a focus on product innovation, sustainable supply chain management and operational efficiency.

Furthermore, Nestlé implements a development strategy involving product innovation, market expansion, and adaptation to consumer trends to achieve sustainability and competitive advantage. Focus on competitive advantage involves a deep understanding of the market and selecting appropriate strategies to maintain the company's position in the competitive market. Nestlé's profile reflects the company's commitment to competitive advantage, sustainability and social responsibility, which are the strategic foundations for long-term growth and success.

The Strategy of PT Nestlé Indonesia to Achieve Competitive Advantage

In facing changes that occur in the company's internal and external environment, companies certainly need to prepare strategies that can be implemented to avoid other problems in the future. PT Nestlé Indonesia has various strategies to overcome problems that occur in the company's external and internal environment. Through its official website, namely Nestle.co.id, Nestle briefly explains the strategies implemented in their business processes. Through the motto "Good Food, Good Life" Nestlé implements various business sustainability strategies, 4 strategies that they always apply in all their companies in the world, namely:

1. Nutrition, Health and Wellness
 2. Emerging markets and PPP
 3. Outdoor leadership
 4. Premiumization
- a. Internal Strategy

In overcoming problems in the internal environment, Nestlé Indonesia implements the following strategies:

1. Implement good governance: Nestlé Indonesia has a good governance system to ensure transparency, accountability and compliance with laws and regulations.
2. Increasing operational efficiency: Nestlé Indonesia continues to innovate and improve operational efficiency to reduce production costs and increase company profits.
3. Improving the quality of human resources: Nestlé Indonesia provides continuous training and development for their employees to improve the quality of human resources in the company.

- b. External Strategy

One of the main external strategies implemented by Nestlé is sustainability. Several of their sustainability programs are explained on the official Nestle.co.id website, such as waste reduction actions, nature protection, and the use of sustainable raw materials for their products. In overcoming problems in the external environment, Nestlé Indonesia implements several strategies, including:

1. Establish strategic partnerships with suppliers and other business partners: Nestlé Indonesia establishes partnerships with suppliers to ensure the availability of quality and sustainable raw materials. Apart from that, Nestlé Indonesia also establishes partnerships with other business partners to increase operational efficiency and effectiveness.

2. Diversifying products: Nestlé Indonesia continues to diversify its products to anticipate changes in consumer tastes and competition with new competitors in the market. Examples include Nestlé milk and coffee products which are very varied and tailored to consumer tastes.

3. Maintain good relationships with regulators and the government: Nestlé Indonesia ensures that their products meet the quality and safety standards set by regulators and the government.

Apart from that, Nestlé Indonesia is also active in promoting healthy food and balanced nutrition, and collaborates with the government on matters related to the food and beverage industry. An example of the efforts made by Nestlé Indonesia to reduce waste is the collaboration between the Karawang Regency Government and KSM Friends of the Environment in building a waste processing site in Karawang. Apart from that, Nestlé Indonesia has also joined Stop Ocean Plastics, and built the BIRU program since 2010 to help local farmers manage cow dung waste.

By implementing these strategies, Nestlé Indonesia can overcome problems that occur in the company's internal and external environment and maintain its position in the market.

CONCLUSIONS, SUGGESTIONS, IMPLICATIONS

In pursuing its vision to be a leader in each of its product categories, Nestlé has demonstrated a strong commitment to competitive advantage, sustainability and social responsibility. Careful analysis of the internal and external environment provides a deep understanding of market dynamics and potential changes. The restructuring process carried out by Nestlé reflects the company's readiness to adapt to market changes and increase operational efficiency.

In facing a dynamic future, Nestlé should continue to improve its sustainability initiatives, especially in sustainable supply chain management and product innovation. The emphasis on corporate social responsibility (CSR) needs to continue to be increased to provide a greater positive impact on society and the environment. In this case, collaboration with stakeholders and implementing responsible business practices can be the key to success.

Strategy formulation is crucial in facing complex business challenges. Nestlé must formulate a strategy that not only includes financial aspects, but also considers the social and environmental impacts of its business decisions. This strategy needs to be able to overcome market dynamics, maintain competitive advantage, and be in line with the company's sustainability mission. Environmental analysis provides invaluable insight into identifying opportunities and threats. Effective control is necessary to ensure sustainability and positive development. Efficient operational aspects support the achievement of company goals. Proactive and responsive management is the key to success in facing ever-changing challenges in the global market. Overall, Nestlé as a leading company must continue to carry out a thorough evaluation of its strategy and operations, focus on sustainability, and maintain a balance between economic growth, social responsibility and environmental sustainability.

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